

FILTRATION EFFECTS OF GRAPHENE NANOPATELETS IN LIQUID MOULDING OF COMPOSITES: PROBLEMS AND POSSIBLE SOLUTIONS

Han Zhang^{1,2}, Yi Liu¹, Arnaud Kernin¹, Emiliano Bilotti^{1,2}, Ton Peijs^{1,2}

¹ School of Engineering and Materials Science, and Materials Research Institute, Queen Mary University of London, Mile End Road, E1 4NS London, UK

² Nanoforce Technology Ltd., Joseph Priestley Building, Queen Mary University of London, Mile End Road, E1 4NS London, UK

Keywords: Graphene nanoplatelets, Nanofillers, Nano-engineered composites, Filtration, Spray coating

Graphene and graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) have attracted numerous attentions in recent years, with many attempts from various industries including aerospace and automotive to utilise this nanofiller to improve components' performance. For carbon/glass fibre composites, two main strategies have been employed when introducing nanofillers such as GNPs to build up hierarchical composites: (i) direct dispersion of nanofillers within bulk epoxy resins prior to resin infusion (top-down); or (ii) depositing nanofillers onto reinforcing carbon/glass fibre preforms (bottom-up). Since it is generally acknowledged that high aspect ratio (length to thickness or diameter ratio) nanofillers are desired to establish high mechanical reinforcement or to create a percolated network for electrical conductivity at low filler content [1-3], relatively large lateral sized GNPs are preferred for composite applications. Furthermore, a uniform dispersion of nanofillers is essential for property enhancements. However, an important issue in the manufacturing of these hybrid micro-nano-engineered composites is the interaction and potential filtration of these nanofillers by the porous micro-sized reinforcing fibres in textile preforms in liquid moulding processes, preventing technology transfer to industrial applications [4].

In this work we demonstrate the filtration of GNPs during resin infusion of nanofiller modified hybrid composites, and for the first time we have successfully quantified this filtration effect by both electrical and optical methods (Fig. 1 and 2). With increased distance away from the resin inlets, an uneven GNPs distribution within the composite laminate is observed from optical transparency mapping (Fig. 1). This is believed to be due to the filtration of GNPs during the resin infusion process where nanoparticles accumulate at regions close to the resin inlet, resulting in less nanofiller passing through the porous fibrous preforms towards the resin outlets. Meanwhile, the electrical conductivity of the composite laminate was maintained at 10^{-6} S/m until a distance of 120 mm away from the inlet, followed by a drop in conductivity with increased distance as a result of an effective reduction in nanofiller (Fig. 2). It is worth noting the consistency between optical and electrical characterizations of the GNP filtration effects. Morphological studies were used to identify the location of the GNPs within the composite laminates, confirming the obtained filtration results (Fig. 3). In addition, an alternative method to introduce GNPs into laminated composites based on an innovative spray coating technique [5, 6] without filtration effects was evaluated (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 Optical transparency of hybrid GFRP/GNP panels, showing an uneven nanofiller distribution with increasing transparency away from the resin inlet (left), together with transparency of a GFRP/GNP laminate made by an alternative spray coating method without filtration effects (right).

Fig. 2 Electrical conductivity and optical transparency map of nano-engineered GFRP/GNP laminates, indicating clear filtration effects and a reduction in electrical conductivity with increasing distance away from the resin inlet point (especially after 120mm).

The quantified results and observations explain why often no obvious filtration is observed in lab-scale panels, but also highlight the significance of the filtration issue for full scale industrial parts. Processing routes need to be developed that allow for the utilization of these nanofillers in composite applications without filtration problems. Based on the obtained

understanding of filtration effects and the presented alternative method of depositing GNPs into inter-laminar regions by spray coating fibre preforms, a novel nano-engineered hybrid composite is developed, which combines the synergistic effect of infused small GNPs for improved inter-tow conductivity with spray-coated large GNPs for inter-laminar conductivity. The electrical, mechanical, as well as multi-functional properties of the developed nano-engineered composites were examined in this work, and the morphological studies were used to identify the location of the GNPs and its reinforcing mechanisms.

Fig. 3 SEM images of hybrid GFRP/GNP composite laminates, showing more connected GNP networks in proximity to the resin inlet (left), while only little traces of GNPs are present near the resin outlet point (right).

REFERENCES

- [1] Bryning MB, Islam MF, Kikkawa JM, Yodh AG. Very low conductivity threshold in bulk isotropic single-walled carbon nanotube-epoxy composites. *Adv Mater.* 2005;17(9):1186-+.
- [2] Sandler JKW, Kirk JE, Kinloch IA, Shaffer MSP, Windle AH. Ultra-low electrical percolation threshold in carbon-nanotube-epoxy composites. *Polymer.* 2003;44(19):5893-5899.
- [3] Zhang H, Bilotti E, Tu W, Lew CY, Peijs T. Static and dynamic percolation of phenoxy/carbon nanotube nanocomposites. *Eur Polym J.* 2015;68(0):128-138.
- [4] da Costa EFR, Skordos AA, Partridge IK, Rezai A. RTM processing and electrical performance of carbon nanotube modified epoxy/fibre composites. *Compos Pt A-Appl Sci Manuf.* 2012;43(4):593-602.
- [5] Zhang H, Liu Y, Kuwata M, Bilotti E, Peijs T. Improved fracture toughness and integrated damage sensing capability by spray coated CNTs on carbon fibre prepreg. *Compos Pt A-Appl Sci Manuf.* 2015;70:102-110.
- [6] Zhang H, Kuwata M, Bilotti E, Peijs T. Integrated damage sensing in fibre-reinforced composites with extremely low carbon nanotube loadings. *J Nanomater.* 2015;2015(Article ID 785834):7.